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“A BUTTERFLY WITH BROKEN WINGS”

She danced once beneath the golden glow,
but now her wings refuse to rise,
her dreams drift where the cold winds blow.

The stars shimmer with tranquil grace,
but fear weighs heavy, hope wears thin,
a silent war she cannot win.

Someday, she'll wake and breathe anew,
No chains to break, no steps erased,
until it's nothing in the end.

And when that day calls out her name,
she'll meet the wind with open wings-
no longer bound, no more the same.